

D4.26 Report from Thematic Meeting IV

WP4

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: DTU, ANSES, INSA

D4.26 REPORT FROM THEMATIC MEETING IV

1. Background

WP4 is responsible (task 4.3 – subtask 4.3.3) for arranging annual thematic integrative meetings (TIMs) between Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs). The aim of these meetings is to facilitate co-operation between sectors and domains by addressing issues experienced challenging to solve. In 2019, the first TIM was arranged in conjunction with the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting on the topic “*Data management and digital innovation*”. The second TIM was held as a webinar in April 2020 on the topic “*Practical use of NGS*”. In 2021 the two JIPs CARE and OH-HARMONY-CAP were asked to set up a workshop together. As a result, the third TIM was held as an online workshop in May 2021 on the subject “*EU surveillance frameworks and infrastructures in a harmonized One Health perspective*”. The fourth and the final thematic meeting was held as an online workshop on February 22, 2022 with the title “*Data Sharing Across Disciplines*”. The aim was to elucidate on the legal aspects of data sharing as well as give examples on solutions to cross-sectoral data sharing.

Subject: Data Sharing Across Disciplines

Theme: Data sharing

Venue: Microsoft Teams TC

Organisers: OHEJP WP4 (ohejp@sva.se)

Target groups: OHEJP project participants, the partner institutes, persons participating in the upcoming OHEJP exercise “SimEx”, and persons interested in data sharing

Number of participants: 120

A Save the Date was created and distributed by the OHEJP Comms Team to the OHEJP Programme Management Team (PMT), Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and JIP/JRP Project Leaders. The invitation, together with the agenda and information on how to register to the event, was sent out on January 24, 2022 by the WP4 and the OHEJP Communication Team. The invitation could be freely forwarded to all persons interested in the subject of data sharing (Appendix 1).

2. Program

9.30-9.40	Short introduction
9.40-10.10	“General challenges regarding data sharing – building blocks that need to be in place” . Kristina Andersson, RISE, Sweden
10.10-10.40	“Challenges and solution for sharing data and models in Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessments” . Laurent Guillier, ANSES, France
10.40-11.00	<i>Break</i>
11.00-12.00	“Sharing data: how to do it in real-life situations” . Serena Faccio, DTU, Denmark. Interactive session targeting actual situations.

3. Objective

The workshop aimed to bring OHEJP project members, the relevant EU institutes and other persons interested in data sharing together to discuss the challenges and potential solutions to problems with cross-sectoral data sharing. Information on the legal aspects of data sharing and encouraging discussions between the meeting delegates were the key objectives.

4. Content

Kristina Andersson from RISE, Sweden presented the general challenges and building blocks for data sharing. Data sharing needs to start from trust: trust between the actors and on the data. It is important to decide on the quantity and quality of data needed. Compliance to the legal requirements is essential. Data sharing is not free, there is always a cost associated with collection and sharing data. Security, with whom and how much to share data, and how and where to store data, need to be thought of. Meta-data, what to include and who decides on meta-data, can be difficult questions. Lastly, skills to analyse, manage and store data are needed. The take-home message from Kristina Andersson was: Build trust and know your data.

Laurent Guillier from Anses, France, spoke about challenges and solutions for sharing data and models in quantitative microbiological risk assessments. Food microbiology researchers, and risk assessment agencies rely on the re-use of domain knowledge like data, models and tools. Based on a survey (carried out in the OHEJP CARE project) of practices in data sharing within risk assessment, such knowledge re-use remains challenging. The adoption of FAIR principles and the development of IT-based solutions will greatly influence future food safety systems. Several OHEJP projects have taken up the challenge of making data and model sharing more accessible and reusable. Interoperability of data, models and tools is an important long term development goal.

Serena Faccio from DTU in Denmark presented examples of data sharing in true situations. Her advice was to avoid confusion between personal data (regulated by the GDPR) and confidential data which is not personal – relating to a person (e.g. data regarding the production of food by a company): both are confidential, but under different rules and perspectives. So-called ‘sensitive’ personal data is defined in Art. 9 in the GDPR and includes data concerning health, broadly interpreted (e.g. a number, symbol or particular assigned to a natural person to uniquely identify the natural person for health purposes; or information derived from the testing or examination of a body part or bodily substance, including from genetic data and biological samples. See Recital 35 to the GDPR. Sharing data across sectors and among public authorities, research institutions and private entities requires trust.

The slides of the three presentations are in the appendixes of this report (Appendix 2-4).

5. Evaluation

The topic of the fourth thematic integrative meeting on challenges in cross-sectoral data sharing interests many persons, as could be seen in the number of delegates registered and

in the lively discussions. The legal challenges with data sharing were familiar to many delegates and they seemed to appreciate that two of the presenters were legal advisers.

In general, the Teams format worked well, even if some participants had some initial issues with accessing the meeting. The meeting delegates were asked to join the meeting in advance and some house-keeping rules were given, such as muting the microphone and switching the camera off if not talking.

6. Attendance

Speakers

Kristina Andersson, RISE, Sweden
Laurent Guillier, ANSES, France
Serena Faccio, DTU, Denmark

OHEJP administration

Karin Artursson, WP4 leader, SVA, Sweden
Elina Lahti, WP4 collaborator, SVA, Sweden
Lena Tuominen, SimEx administrator, SVA, Sweden

Other participants

Altogether 120 participants from 16 countries: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, the United Kingdom from institutes within public health, food safety and animal health as well as from EFSA and EMA.